

RECONSTRUCTION OF PMH'S UNLAWFUL ACTS AS A *BRIDGE OF COHERENCE* IN FAMILY LAW PLURALISM THROUGH JUDICIAL INSTRUMENTALITY ON THE BREACH OF CUSTOMARY MARRIAGE PROMISES AND ANALYSIS OF THE DECISION OF THE KEFAMENANU DISTRICT COURT NUMBER 10 PDT.G 2025 PN KFM

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ABSTRACT

Legal pluralism in Indonesia requires synergy between Positive Law (Article 1365 of the Civil Code, Marriage Law) and Living Law. In the realm of family law, the formalistic rigidity of Article 2 of Law No. 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage creates a norm gap (void of norms) that nullifies pre-marital bonds that are customarily mature (especially after adata agreement) in the Atoni Meto community, TTU. This rigidity causes victims of abandonment (breach of marriage vows) to not receive adequate legal protection. This normative juridical research, using a legislative and conceptual approach, aims to formulate a model of normative coherence reconstruction through an analytical perspective analysis. An empirical case study of the Kefamenanu District Court Decision Number 10/Pdt.G/2025/PN Kfm was used to test the model. This study found that Unlawful Acts (PMH) function as an effective bridge of normative coherence. Through judicial instrumentality and progressive legal principles, Judge Kefamenanu implemented the expansion of the interpretation of the element of "unlawful" (since the Arrest Hoge Raad of January 31, 1919) which includes violations of propriety and living norms (Living Law). Violations of customary obligations Pre-marriage are categorized as onrechtmatiggedaad, providing legal standing for the victim. The success of this model led to the hybridization of sanctions, in which courts converted customary sanctions of a communal nature ("cover-up" fines) into formal civil indemnity obligations. This model progressively guarantees the recovery of material and immaterial losses (dignity) of victims, while affirming the coercion of Customary Law in the formal justice system.

Keywords: *Breach of Marriage Promise, Customary Law, Kefamenanu District Court Decision, Judicial Instrumentality, Progressive Law, Unlawful Acts (PMH), Living Law.*